

Jute Seeds—*Corchorus Capsularis*. Part I.

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There are two varieties of the jute plant—*Corchorus capsularis* and *Corchorus olitorius*—the seeds of which can be differentiated by their physical appearance. The former are larger in size and of a nut-brown colour, while the latter are of a blue-black colour. *Corchorus capsularis* seeds, procured from the Government Agricultural Farm at Manipur, Dacca, were used in the present investigation.

The seeds are found throughout Bengal. The present price of the seeds is about Rs. 20 per maund. According to Dymock, the seeds possess medicinal properties. In India the seeds, which have a bitter taste, are administered in doses of about 80 grains in cases of fever and obstruction of the abdominal viscera. In spite of these properties it appears that a thorough chemical study of the seeds has not yet been undertaken, though a beginning was made by Kobert (*Ber. Natur. Ges. Rostock; Arch. Freunde Natur. Ges. Mecklenburg*, 1906, No 5 ; *vide Chem. Zentr.*, 1907, I, 1273) and by Tsuno (*Monatsh. pr. Tierheilkunde*, 1895, 6, 455) who seem to have isolated an impure, amorphous, bitter stuff, under the name of Corchorin, having strongly toxic properties. None of the authors seems to have isolated the oil which is contained in the seed. The present author has therefore undertaken a chemical study of the seeds.

As the seeds when subjected to a high pressure did not yield any oil but were converted into a stiff paste, the powdered seeds were exhaustively extracted with hot petroleum ether in a Soxhlet's apparatus. The residue left after distilling off the petrol was a yellowish brown viscid oil which could not be distilled without decomposition and was free from any readily volatile matter. The oil, which belongs to the class of fixed semi-drying oils, slowly sets to a rubber-like elastic mass in contact with air, but out of contact with it, it can be preserved indefinitely. The oil is free from the bitter taste of the seeds.

After extraction with petroleum ether, the seeds were extracted repeatedly with rectified spirit in a Soxhlet's apparatus. The seeds thus lost their bitter taste. On evaporation of the alcoholic extract

to a small volume and addition of acetone to the solution, a yellowish white viscous mass was precipitated: it readily absorbs moisture and turns brown in the air. The substance thus obtained was crystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetone as perfectly white crystals which are hygroscopic and readily soluble in water. It tastes somewhat sweet at first, but a bitter after-taste is soon developed. It does not reduce Fehling's solution, but on hydrolysis with dilute mineral acid reduces the solution quite readily even in the cold. In all its chemical properties it corresponds to a glucoside. Besides glucose another substance, insoluble in water, is produced as a product of hydrolysis.

The acetone-alcoholic mother-liquor, on evaporation, yielded another colourless substance which has an extremely bitter taste. It was not obtained in sufficient quantities for investigation but experiments with larger quantities are now in progress. It gives a bluish green colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and does not reduce Fehling's solution. But on hydrolysis with mineral acids an insoluble product is obtained and a sugar which reduces Fehling's solution on heating. From these properties it seems probable that this substance is identical with that with which Kobert worked (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

(a) *Characteristics of the Seeds.*

Moisture	...	...	7.1 per cent.
Ash (aluminium, potassium and phosphoric acid were detected)	...	...	6.0 per cent.
Volatile oil	...	...	traces.
Fixed oil (extracted with petroleum ether)	...	...	14.78 per cent.

(b) *Characteristics of the Fixed Oil.*

Specific gravity at 28°C	...	...	0.921
Viscosity at 28°C	...	...	58.1417 relative to water.
Refractive index at 30°C	...	...	1.4705
Optical rotation	...	...	0.0
Saponification value	...	...	184.4
Iodine value (Wij's method)	...	...	109.2
Acid value	...	...	24.07
Unsaponifiable matter	...	...	3.0 per cent.

The solubility and the reactions of the fixed oil are as follows:—

The crude oil was found to be insoluble in water, alcohol, cold glacial acetic acid, dilute sulphuric and nitric acids but readily soluble in ether, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, amyl alcohol and in pyridine. The crude oil was emulsified with sodium carbonate solution and saponified with sodium hydroxide in the cold. Sulphuric acid gives a brown colour which on dilution with water separates a white, gelatinous, light solid. With cold nitric acid part of the oil floats and part goes in solution with a light yellow colour which on dilution with water gives a semi-solid substance. The oil is gradually decolourised by bromine water in the cold and a butter-like substance is produced. With potassium permanganate solution immediate decolourisation takes place in the cold. In the elaidin test the oil yielded a buttery mass separating from a fluid portion after thirty minutes. Metallic sodium produces a brisk action on the ethereal solution of the oil and a white substance separates.

Extraction of the Seeds with Alcohol.

The seeds after being extracted with hot petrol were extracted with hot alcohol (90 per cent.). The alcoholic solution was filtered and on addition of acetone to the concentrated extract a white gum-like substance separated.

The substance gradually turns brown in air. It contains carbon hydrogen and oxygen only. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish brown colour: on adding water nothing separates. The substance does not reduce Fehling's solution. Strong hydrochloric acid dissolves it with a port wine colour and the dilute solution reduces Fehling's solution immediately.

It was crystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetone in perfectly colourless crystals, which are hygroscopic and readily soluble in water. It is insoluble in acetone, petroleum ether, ethyl ether and absolute alcohol, but soluble in glacial acetic acid and in alcohol (60 per cent.). The substance decolourises potassium permanganate solution. On hydrolysis by dilute mineral acids the substance is decomposed into glucose and another colourless substance insoluble in water. Evidently the substance is a glucoside. It shrinks at 98° and decomposes with evolution of gas at 105° and shows a dextro rotation of 108°·6 ($[\alpha]_D^{20} = +108\cdot6$). It gives a yellow brown colour with sulphuric acid. This substance is now being further examined. (Found: C, 81·16 ; H, 9·65 per cent.).

Summary and Conclusions.

The oil extracted from the jute seeds with petroleum ether is a non-volatile fixed oil possessing properties very similar to the semi-drying class of oils. It is unsaturated, with a high iodine value, and is readily saponified by caustic alkalis. From the oxidation of the free acids, it seems highly probable that the oil consists of a large proportion of the glycerides of the unsaturated fatty acids such as oleic, linolic and linolenic acids. Further investigation of the oil is now in progress.

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